

RAW BLOT IMAGES corresponding to main and supplementary figures from the article titled: *Insufficiency of 40S ribosomal proteins, RPS26 and RPS25 negatively affects biosynthesis of polyglycine-containing proteins in fragile-X associated conditions* (Tutak K et al., 2024, eLife)

Images corresponding to **Figure 1**:

Images corresponding to **Figure 2**:

Images corresponding to **Figure 3**:

Images corresponding to **Figure 4**:

G

Images corresponding to **Figure 5**:

B

C

Images corresponding to **Figure 6**:

Images corresponding to **Supplementary Figure 1:**

Images corresponding to **Supplementary Figure 2:**

Images corresponding to **Supplementary Figure 3**:

Images corresponding to **Supplementary Figure 4:**

Images corresponding to **Supplementary Figure 5:**

